

Equilibrium Study of the Complex Formation of some Bivalent Transition Metal Ions with Sulphur Oxygen Donor Ligands

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In the present paper, we report the stability constants of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with thiomalic acid (TMA), thioglycolic acid (TGA), and thiolactic acid (TLA) determined potentiometrically in aqueous medium at a fixed ionic strength $\mu=0.1 M$ ($NaClO_4$) at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Experimental

The solution of TMA (Evans) was prepared by direct weighing and those of TGA (Sisco) and TLA (Fluka) from the stock solutions by diluting a calculated quantity of the acids with conductivity-water. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade. Metal ion and perchloric acid (0.04 M) solutions were standardised by usual procedures¹. Ferrous sulphate solution was freshly prepared for each titration. A Phillips PR 9405 M pH-meter (accuracy ± 0.05 pH) with glass-calomel electrode assembly was used to measure the pH. Procedure for the pH-metric study was similar to that reported earlier². Constants were calculated by the procedure of Irving and Rossotti^{3,4}. The proton-ligand stability constants, $\log K_1^H$, $\log K_2^H$ and $\log K_3^H$ (for TMA only), and stepwise formation constants ($\log K_n$) of their complexes at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$ are presented in Table 1. The literature values are comparable with the values reported⁴.

Results and Discussion

First and second deprotonation of TLA and TGA correspond to those of COOH and SH groups, respectively. For TMA, the first two steps involve the release of two COOH protons and the third step involves the deprotonation of SH group.

For Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} -TMA, -TGA and -TLA systems, the $\bar{n}$ values varied between 0.1 and 1.9, thereby indicating the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. In Mn^{II} -TMA, -TGA and -TLA systems, the $\bar{n}$ values varied between 0.1 and 0.9, resulting in the formation of 1:1 complex only. Reddy and Bhattacharya⁵ also reported the formation of 1:1 complex between Mn^{II} and TMA. In Cu^{II} -TMA, -TGA and -TLA systems, the actual $\bar{n}$ values obtained are between 0.9 and 1.9, indicating thereby the formation of the 1:2 complex in a single step.

Stability constants decrease with the increase of temperature and thus lower temperature is favourable for the complex formation. Metal-ligand

stability constants also decrease with an increase in ionic strength of the medium (except Fe^{II} -TLA system).

The high positive values of $\log K_1/K_2$ (Table 1) may be assigned to $M \rightarrow L, \pi$ -bonding⁶. The order of stability was found in the ligand order, TMA > TGA > TLA. The increased stability of TMA complexes may be due to the terdentate nature of the ligand. In general, the stability constant values were in accordance with Irving-Williams⁷ order. However, with TGA ligand, higher stability in Co^{II} complex as compared to that of Ni^{II} was observed.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES
Temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1 M$ ($NaClO_4$)

Proton-ligand constants		TMA	TGA	TLA			
Ligand							
	pK_1^H	8.81	9.88	9.62			
	pK_2^H	4.11	2.92	3.24			
	pK_3^H	8.12	—	—			
Metal-ligand constants :							
Ligand	Constants	Mn^{II}	Fe^{II}	Co^{II}	Ni^{II}	Cu^{II}	Zn^{II}
TMA	$\log K_1$	4.50	5.85	6.56	6.49	7.06	7.04
	$\log K_2$	—	4.91	5.50	5.79	6.39	6.39
TGA	$\log K_1$	3.79	5.32	8.25	6.98	10.01	8.01
	$\log K_2$	—	4.08	6.08	5.90	8.65	7.25
TLA	$\log K_1$	2.44	6.32	7.26	6.65	9.19	7.64
	$\log K_2$	—	4.95	5.08	6.15	8.29	6.91

Standard deviation = ± 0.09 .

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